

Data Management Plan Information

La Chouffe DMP New

This DMP has been created for managing data representative within the Open Publishing domain in the context of the [Open Science](#) exam at the University of Bologna. Starting from our research questions related to scientometric studies, we aim at evaluating the management of the state-of-the-art of data about academic articles and to understand how much aggregators (in our case, the Directory of Open Access Journals, [DOAJ](#), and [Crossref](#)) present shared information.

The DOAJ acts as an umbrella organisation that aims to increase the visibility of Open Access journals. They have an [API](#) and a [public data dump](#) with the information about both articles from their journals and journals themselves.

Crossref is an organisation that aims at making scientific communication better; they have aggregated huge quantities of metadata of articles and, for some, their reference lists. In this context, we used their [REST API](#).

Our research involves the articles from Open Access journals in DOAJ and their data on Crossref. The produced datasets will be created by manipulating both datasets.

The datasets, methods used to gather them and further information will be available on Github (as a reference, [here is the Github repository](#))

Funder

None

Grant

none

Organisations

Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna

Researchers

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Datasets

Title: DOAJ and Crossref Aggregated Data

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset contains the data from articles in DOAJ organised in journals' ISSN and with the data from Crossref.

In particular, it will contain:

1. ISSN
2. DOI
3. Publication Year
4. Number of References
5. Reference List (with information about assertion)
6. Entity responsible for assertion of DOI
7. Presence of article in Crossref

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information
- This data will be used to gather information for our research.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

• reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

- Data will be gathered from dumps made available by DOAJ and from DOAJ's API

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files, Numerical
 - It will contain data about the year of publication, the presence of the article in Crossref, the reference list and the origin of the DOI.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- GB (gigabyte)
 - It will likely be bigger than the data straight from the DOAJ.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Industry
 - This data can be useful to both replicate the study or to gather new insights on the world of Open Access publication

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
 - Dublin Core
 - We will use Dublin Core as it provides a general purpose and potent way to describe the Data.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- No
 - We will not use standardised categories as we want more flexibility

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be available freely.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be hosted on Zenodo.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

- No
 - We want more flexibility

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will provide version numbers according to Semantic Versioning.

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - Yes, we will use DOIs provided by Zenodo.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- Yes
 - It will be stored in Zenodo.

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

- Linked Open Data
- OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

- Yes
 - 8-bit ASCII Text

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will use json, an open format.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 - There are multiple, one is Sublime Text.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

- Yes
 - We will describe the quality of data available.

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes
 - Described data will be accessible through Github

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- GitHub
 - We will make the data available through Github or other online repositories if the data is too large.

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery
 - We will consider a different backup storage if the data cannot be stored on Github

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

- No
 - We will try to have a more flexible vocabulary.

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project
 - The data will be available at least at the end of the project.

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

We will use CC0 v.1.0

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

- Yes
 - We will describe how we obtained the data, allowing anyone to verify the quality of it.

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

Data conform to format specification, Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes
 - We will support anyone who decides to reuse our data. If any help is needed, feel free to contact us or open an issue on Github.

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes
 - Two people in particular are in charge for the creation and quality of the data.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
- Supervision and Best Practices

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
- Software and Data Production

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
- Software and Data Production

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive, Other, Personal Archive
 - Data will be available on Github, but we will consider multiple storages with the help of our institution.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

Title: La Software

Template: Horizon 2020

This software will be used to enrich our datasets, by first cleaning the DOAJ dataset, then connecting to the API of Crossref and ultimately extract knowledge from those passages.

It will be coded in the Python programming language.

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information, To share information, To develop a product
 - This is a software developed to perform scientometric analyses on our DOAJ and Crossref data. It will be divided in components aimed at managing different stages of the manipulation and compare the data obtained.

It will be developed using the Python programming language and its libraries. All of these will be listed in the dedicated repo. The development of those scripts can also be found in the [Open Science](#) repositories under the team La Chouffe.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- experimental (e.g., gene sequencing data), simulation (e.g., climate modeling data)
 - The data will be the scripts employed in creating the other two datasets, cleaning them and performing analysis on them.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Software
 - Scripts programmed in Python.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- MB (megabyte)
 - It is reasonable to expect that the data will be at most some MB.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Industry
- The dat

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
 - We will use FRBR to describe our software.
- Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.2 Please provide URL/Location describing the used metadata schema

- <https://vocab.org/frbr/core>

- FRBR

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- No
 - We will not use standardised vocabularies because we want flexibility

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

- Yes
 - We will make the metadata about our software freely available

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

- Yes
 - We will host all our metadata on Zenodo

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

- No
 - We will try to keep maximum flexibility.

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will follow [Semantic Versioning](#) to maintain a rigorous development of our software.

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - We will use DOIs provided by entities like Zenodo.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- Yes
 - We will provide it in containers such as Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

- Linked Open Data
- OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

- Yes
- 8-bit ASCII Text

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will create .py files.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 - Any text editor can be used to open .py files e.g. Sublime Text

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

- Yes
 - We will describe the development of software, providing the reasoning behind them.

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

- No
 - The code created will have an Open License, allowing for free reuse.

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes
 - The data will be accessible on Github.

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- GitHub
 - The data will be hosted in a repository in Github, in particular in the global [Open Science](#) repository.

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery

- We will have our scripts on Github and in local repositories.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

at end of project

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project
- The data will be available during development and, globally, by the end of the project.

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

We are currently discussing which license to choose. The ones we will probably use are the [ISC](#) license or the [MIT](#).

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

- Yes
- We will describe how we created our software in our Jupyter Notebooks and in our Workflow.

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

Use of tools for automatic checks

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes
- We will provide support to any future users. If support is needed, one can open a Github issue.

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure, Other
- If more support is needed to cover the data, we will try to apply for grants or ask for support to our institution.

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- Yes
 - Two people are tasked with the development of the software and its maintenance.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

- a.
- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
 - Supervision and Best Practices
- b.
- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
 - Software Development and Data Gathering
- c.
- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
 - Software Development and Data Gathering

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Other, Personal Archive
- Hosted on Github
 - Data reuse will be assured by using personal storage as well as hosting on Github.

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

- Yes
 - While we will use an open license, we have authorship over this software.

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: DOAJ data

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset will be created combining the dump retrieved from DOAJ, removing the unnecessary information, in order for it to be updated with the data from Crossref. In particular it will contain:

DOI of the article

ISSN associated with the article

Year of creation

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To combine with other data
- This data will be used in combination with data retrieved from Crossref's API.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

• reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

- The data will be secondary data, curated by DOAJ.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files, Numerical
- The dataset will contain:

DOIs (Direct Object Identifier) about each article contained in DOAJ. A [DOI](#) is a unique identifier for an article, a software, a DMP...

ISSN (International Standard Serial Number): a unique identifier for a periodical publication.

Year of publication.

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

- GB (gigabyte)
 - The whole json file for the articles in DOAJ weights about 20 GB. While we will strip articles from unnecessary data, it is reasonable to assume it won't be lower than 1 GB.

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Industry
 - This data could be reused by researchers interested in the context of Open Science, or to better evaluate the contributions of Open Access articles to the academic world, maybe combining it with other sources or going the other way around (from Crossref to DOAJ, using these articles). Moreover, it can be used to verify how rigorous our analysis was.

The choice of the CC0 license follows this idea as well.

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes
 - Dublin Core
 - We will describe the data by following Dublin Core. This is a well known standard that ensures flexibility.

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- No
 - While we will use metadata from Dublin Core, we will not employ a standard vocabulary as we want the description to be flexible. We will consider employing standardised vocabularies in the future.

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be freely available.

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be freely harvestable from Zenodo.

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

- No
 - We want to be flexible in naming the files.

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

- Yes
 - We will follow the [Semantic Versioning](#) standard for naming the dataset

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes
 - We will use DOIs provided by Zenodo.

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

- Yes
 - The metadata will be contained in Zenodo.

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

- Linked Open Data
- OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

- Yes
 - 8-bit ASCII Text

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - We will use .json, an open format easy to reuse.

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

- Yes
 - One can use many different open source softwares to access json files. As an example, Sublime Text.

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

- Yes
 - We will provide a description of the quality of the data, open to other informations.

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

- No

- We will not use personal data.

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

- Yes

- We will make the data openly accessible and downloadable.

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other

- GitHub

- We will consider using other repositories if it will not be possible to host the whole repository on Github.

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

- insecure with backup and recovery

- We will consider hosting a backup in a different service.

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

- No

- The data will be available without using an access point.

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

No

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

- end of project

- The data will be readily accessible by the end of the project, if not earlier

3.1.4.4 What internationally recognised licence(s) will you use for the described data?

CC0 v.1.0

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

- Yes

- We will document each passage in the creation of the data, assuring the reproducibility and verifiability of consistency of data.

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

Data conform to format specification, Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes

- We will make data available for anyone to access and reuse; anyone can contact us if support is needed.

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- No

- Two people will mainly be responsible for the production of software and data. They will be responsible for its maintenance.

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)
- Supervision of processes, Best practices

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)
- Responsible for Software and Production of Data

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)
- Responsible for Software and Production of Data

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

- Institutional archive, Other, Personal Archive
- We will publish the data on open repositories. If a migration will be needed, we will consider asking for support to our institution

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No